

graphia

GRAPHIA

Knowledge Graphs, AI Services and Next Generation Instrumentation for R&D in Social Sciences and Humanities

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GRAPHIA Policy Brief 1

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Table of Contents

Deliverable Information	2
Change Log	2
List of Abbreviations	4
Executive Summary	5
1. Introduction	6
2. Policy Recommendations	8
2.1 Implementation of research infrastructures	8
2.2 Access to research infrastructures	8
2.3 Funding of research infrastructures	8
2.4 International co-operation of research infrastructures	9
2.5 Employment and skills in research infrastructures	9
2.6 Greening of research infrastructures	9
2.7 Interaction of research infrastructures with industry	9
2.8 ERIC legal framework	10
2.9 Technology development, data and digital services, digitalisation	10
2.10 Level of connection of your RI to EOSC	11
2.11 Contribution to other research areas and to broader EU priorities	11
2.12 Sustainability of research infrastructures	11
3. References	12
4. Contact Details	13

List of Abbreviations

AI - Artificial Intelligence
APIs - Application Programming Interfaces
EC - European Commission
EOSC - European Open Science Cloud
ESFRI - European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
EU - European Union
FAIR - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
IPLs - Innovation Prototyping Labs
LLM4SSH - Large Language Models for SSH
NLP - Natural Language Processing
PN - Pelagios Network
RDA - Research Data Alliance
RDF - Resource Description Framework
RIs - Research Infrastructures
R&D - Research & Development
SKG-IF - Scientific Knowledge Graph – Interoperability Framework
SMEs - Small to Medium Enterprises
SSH - Social Sciences and Humanities
SSHOC - SSH Open Marketplace
SPAR Ontologies - Semantic Publishing and Referencing Ontologies
SPARQL - SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language

Executive Summary

This policy brief draws on the first 16 months of [GRAPHIA](#) - *Knowledge Graphs, Artificial Intelligence (AI) Services and Next Generation Instrumentation for Research & Development (R&D) in Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH)* - a 36-month Horizon Europe project, to set out recommendations for strengthening digital research infrastructures in SSH. Its central message: the SSH community now has the technical means to overcome long-standing data fragmentation, but realising this potential depends on targeted and sustained European Union (EU) policy support.

The evidence base is GRAPHIA's progress to date. The project is building the first federated knowledge graph for SSH, connecting heterogeneous data from five research infrastructures (OPERAS, EHRI, E-RIHS, RESILIENCE and GGP) through a federated gateway and the Scientific Knowledge Graph - Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF). It has delivered the foundational reference model (the GRAPHIA Ontology and Technical Architecture), a catalogue of next-generation SSH instruments, and domain-specific AI services such as Large Language Models for SSH (LLM4SSH) and an SSH Citation Index. In parallel, use cases demonstrating the added value of the SSH Knowledge Graph and associated instruments are being developed. Eight, including both industry and academia, were identified at the time of writing the project proposal (EHRI, CNRS MAP, Cyprus institute, CNR, GGP and GESIS, Genius Loci, Resilience and OAEBUDT). These will be described and published as part of a report due at the end of the project. Through 2025 and 2026, 12 further viable commercial SSH use cases were published as part of the Industry Hub.

On this basis, the brief makes three recommendations to EU decision-makers: sustain investment in open-source, Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (FAIR)-compliant data infrastructure for SSH; support interoperability standards that enable cross-Research Infrastructures (RI) federation; and establish bridging instruments between project-based R&D and the long-term operational funding of shared digital services.

1. Introduction

CALL: HORIZON-RIA - HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions

TOPIC: HORIZON-INFRA-2024-TECH-01-01 - R&D for the next generation of scientific instrumentation, tools, methods, solutions for RI upgrade

PROJECT: [GRAPHIA](#) - Knowledge Graphs, AI Services and Next Generation Instrumentation for Research and Development in Social Sciences and Humanities

PROJECT SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES:

- Raising SSH RIs capacity by building a shared environment for next-generation technologies uptake
- Support transformative research addressing key societal challenges as defined in EU policies with innovative instrumentations and AI-driven data platforms
- Create a unique collaborative space between SSH RIs and industry to foster value-added services co-creation
- Accelerating industries' uptake of advanced technologies for social and cultural data markets
- Integrate SSH RIs into innovation ecosystems on local, regional and global levels

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Highlights

- **SSH Knowledge Graph & Federation:** GRAPHIA builds the first federated knowledge graph for SSH, connecting heterogeneous data from five ESFRIs (OPERAS, EHRI, E-RIHS, RESILIENCE, GGP) through a federated gateway and the SKG-IF - enabling cross-domain discovery across previously siloed research data.
- **Next-Gen Instrumentation & AI Services:** The project develops and upgrades scientific instrumentation for SSH data acquisition (3D scanning, spectroscopy,

digital twins), alongside domain-specific AI services including LLM4SSH, an SSH Citation Index, and AI modules for knowledge graph enrichment.

- **Industry Co-Creation & Real-World Use Cases:** Through IPLs, a public call for pilots, and concrete use cases spanning cultural heritage, social sciences, publishing and geospatial data, GRAPHIA creates a structured model for RI–industry collaboration involving commercial partners and SMEs.
- **Policy Recommendation:** GRAPHIA recommends sustained EU investment in open-source, FAIR-compliant data infrastructure for SSH, interoperability standards enabling cross-RI federation, and bridging instruments between project-based R&D and long-term operational funding for shared digital services.

2. Policy Recommendations

2.1 Implementation of research infrastructures

GRAPHIA has delivered foundational outputs that advance the technological readiness of SSH research infrastructures: the [GRAPHIA Ontology](#) and the [Technical Architecture](#) define the reference model for the SSH Knowledge Graph, while the [Catalogue of Next-Generation SSH Instruments and Tools](#) provides an inventory of upgraded instrumentation across partner RIs. These results directly strengthen the operational capacities of the five participating ESFRIs. Because they are openly published and standards-based, these outputs are reusable beyond the consortium: any SSH research infrastructure can adopt the same reference model to align its data with the federation, turning project-level results into a transferable template for cross-RI harmonisation at European scale. A key remaining challenge is the heterogeneity of data models and maturity levels across SSH RIs, which GRAPHIA addresses through its interoperability framework based on SKG-IF. We recommend that future EU calls continue supporting cross-RI technology harmonisation projects, particularly for RIs transitioning from project-based to permanent operation.

2.2 Access to research infrastructures

GRAPHIA will broaden access to SSH research data by making the SSH Knowledge Graph openly accessible via semantic query language and protocol for databases (SPARQL) endpoints, application programming interfaces (APIs) and a codesigned web interface. The first public release of the SSH Knowledge Graph is planned for August 2026. User needs have been elicited through qualitative interviews and six codesign workshops (October 2025-June 2026), ensuring that GRAPHIA's services meet the requirements of researchers, data providers and industry users. After the project, the SSH Knowledge Graph and associated services will be sustained through OPERAS and the partner RIs. We recommend that the European Commission (EC) encourages FAIR-by-design access services in future RI calls and supports the sustainability of open data platforms beyond project funding periods.

2.3 Funding of research infrastructures

GRAPHIA's consortium model, combining ESFRIs with SMEs and industry associations, demonstrates a viable co-funding approach where public RIs and private entities

co-invest in shared digital infrastructure. The call for pilots mechanism attracts external organisations willing to invest resources in applying the SSH Knowledge Graph to their own use cases. We recommend that future EU funding instruments incentivise such mixed public–private co-investment models, and that INFRA calls provide bridging support between project-based R&D and operational deployment of shared digital services.

2.4 International co-operation of research infrastructures

GRAPHIA integrates knowledge graphs from international partners including OpenCitations (UNIBO, Italy) and the Open Research Knowledge Graph (TIB, Germany). The project's SKG-IF is developed in close cooperation with the Research Data Alliance (RDA) and aligns with international standards such as Semantic Publishing and Referencing Ontologies ([SPAR Ontologies](#)). These efforts contribute to global challenges around open access to data and digitalisation of research. We recommend that the EC continues to support interoperability framework development as a vehicle for international RI cooperation.

2.5 Employment and skills in research infrastructures

GRAPHIA organises training workshops and webinars on knowledge graph technologies, AI for SSH, and FAIR data management. The IPLs serve as capacity-building events where RI staff, researchers and industry professionals develop practical skills in co-creation settings. The [first IPL](#) took place in Zadar (October 2025) and the second is planned for Brussels (September 2026). We recommend that EU programmes recognise and support skills development as a structural component of RI investment, particularly in emerging areas such as AI and knowledge engineering.

2.6 Greening of research infrastructures

Not applicable. Greening has not been a specific focus of GRAPHIA to date.

2.7 Interaction of research infrastructures with industry

Industry engagement is a core pillar of GRAPHIA. The project includes seven commercial partners (Foxcub, Net7, e-SDF, Odoma, ICF, KGA, Genius Loci) and has launched a public call for pilots to attract SMEs and enterprises interested in building

applications on the SSH knowledge graph. These efforts resulted in 12 industry use cases showcased as part of the [Industry Hub](#) launched in June 2026 that will be further enriched based on more use cases as the project progresses. The IPLs, led by Industry Commons Foundation, create a structured co-creation space between academia and industry. Across the various activities, more than 60 commercial organisations have participated and provided feedback so far in the project. We recommend that future INFRA calls maintain and strengthen dedicated mechanisms for RI–industry collaboration, and support the development of data spaces that bridge public research data and commercial applications.

2.8 ERIC legal framework

During this first phase, the ERIC legal framework did not directly affect the project’s key results. However, it is considered one of the most promising options for ensuring the long-term sustainability, coordination and governance of service operations once they have been integrated into the OPERAS service portfolio.

2.9 Technology development, data and digital services, digitalisation

GRAPHIA delivers technological advances across three domains. First, a hybrid knowledge graph architecture combining Resource Description Framework (RDF) and Labelled Property Graph technologies, with the [GRAPHIA Ontology](#), a [Federated Gateway](#) for cross-graph queries, and QLever as a high-performance open-source SPARQL engine. Second, next-generation scientific instrumentation for SSH data acquisition, including upgraded 3D scanning, spectroscopy and digital twin technologies for cultural heritage research, catalogued in the deliverable [3.1](#). Third, AI services tailored to SSH: LLM4SSH, an [SSH Citation Index](#), Natural Language Processing (NLP) modules for automated entity extraction and classification, and AI modules for knowledge graph enrichment. We recommend sustained investment in open-source graph technologies, domain-specific AI models, and scientific instrumentation co-developed between RIs and industry as critical enablers for European research competitiveness.

2.10 Level of connection of your RI to EOSC

Several GRAPHIA partners are members of the EOSC Association and contribute to EOSC Task Forces. GRAPHIA tools and services will be registered on the SSH Open Marketplace (SSHOC) and made discoverable through EOSC. The project's Persistent Identifier strategy and FAIR [data management plan](#) ensure alignment with EOSC policies. GRAPHIA's SKG-IF is designed to be compatible with EOSC-based federation principles. We recommend that the EOSC Tripartite Governance provide clearer guidance, through the EOSC Federation Handbook, on how domain-specific knowledge graphs can be integrated as first-class resources within the EOSC Federation.

2.11 Contribution to other research areas and to broader EU priorities

As part of the GRAPHIA activities, collaborations with other projects and efforts have been established. The first and second IPL are held in collaboration with the [LUMEN](#) project. Additionally, the collaboration with LUMEN expanded into the development of [personas](#) (design, data collection, dissemination campaign alignment). Other projects have also been contacted to discuss potential collaboration and alignment, such as (but not limited to) [FASCA](#) and [ATRIUM](#). A new collaboration was established between GRAPHIA and the [Pelagios Network \(PN\)](#), a global community of practice and bottom-up infrastructure developing the ways and means of linking heritage data online. Project partner Odoma was invited to take over the coordination of PN's Registry working group, together with a representative from Archaeology Data Service as a junior coordinator. A collaboration was initiated with the [Artificial Intelligence for Libraries, Archives & Museums](#) group with an initial event organised together in April 2026, joining their mailing list where GRAPHIA shares relevant news as well as investigating other ways of potential collaboration. We recommend projects are encouraged to find and foster such connections to ensure cross-collaborations and joint innovation.

2.12 Sustainability of research infrastructures

GRAPHIA's approach to sustainability focuses on ensuring the continued relevance, accessibility, and usability of its outputs beyond the funded duration of the project. As outlined in the Description of Action, this includes both technical and organisational

measures for long-term integration into European research infrastructures and reuse by diverse stakeholder communities. Several sustainability mechanisms are in place or under development: stewardship models, permissive open source licenses, repositories, partnerships, and similar. Sustainability planning will continue to evolve throughout the project and will be reviewed regularly. A refined strategy, including confirmed governance structures and post-project hosting arrangements, will be presented in the final policy deliverable (December 2027).

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Websites:

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- <https://graphia-ssh.eu/industry-hub/>
- <https://lumenproject.eu/>
- <https://www.oscars-project.eu/projects/fasca-facilitating-scholarly-communication-analysis-through-gotriple-pipeline>
- <https://atrium-research.eu/>
- <https://pelagios.org/about-us/working-groups>

4. Contact Details

For further information, interested stakeholders can contact the project via the email address: contact@graphia-ssh.eu.